

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

Proposal No.: 848261

Deliverable D7.4: Final Report on RCT, Dissemination, Communication and Community Building

Deliverable No. D22 – WP7

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Target Dissemination Level	Public
Status of the Document	Version 1

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1 Introduction

This deliverable will be a final document summarizing the results of the RCT (Randomized Clinical Trial), the UNITI dissemination activities, communication and community building activities.

2 Result of the RCT

The manuscript of the RCT-paper that describes the clinical results of the RCT is in preparation. It is planned to submit the paper by end of August. The results of the RCT can be read in detail after successful publication; only the abstract of the paper is printed below.

Summary of the RCT results:

Due to a broad spectrum of etiologies, phenotypes, and underlying pathophysiological mechanisms, no uniform causal treatment for tinnitus is available. A combination of treatments, enabling a concurrent therapy of different causes, might provide a viable and superior treatment strategy.

We conducted a multicenter, parallel-arm, randomized clinical trial involving patients with chronic subjective tinnitus. Patients were randomly assigned to a single or combinational treatment. We used a set of four different therapy approaches: cognitive-behavioral therapy, hearing aids, structured counseling, and sound therapy. All possible combinations of two treatments were tested. The primary outcome was the change from baseline to week 12 in the total score of the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI).

A total of 461 patients were enrolled; 230 were assigned to single and 231 to combinational treatments. The mean total THI scores at baseline were 48.5 for the single and 47.4 for the combinational treatment group. Least mean square changes from baseline to week 12 were -11.9 for single (95% confidence interval [CI], -14.7 to -9.1) and -14.9 for combinational treatments (95% CI, -17.8 to -12.0), with a between-group difference of 3 points (95% CI, 0.01 to 6.1; $p = 0.051$). THI scores decreased for each treatment group from baseline to week 12. No serious adverse events occurred.

In this trial involving patients with chronic tinnitus, a combination of two treatments tended to reduced tinnitus-related handicap more than single treatment applications after 12 weeks ($p = 0.051$).

3 UNITI Dissemination Activities

As described in the second periodic report of the project the consortium member VIL has designed and constituted the common UNITI strategy towards efficient project visibility and measurable communication actions. This task included i) the analysis and segmentation of the target audience, ii) the selection of the communication techniques best suited to reach each of these segments, iii) the elaboration of the UNITI Dissemination plan in line with the exploitation activities. The Dissemination plan (Deliverable D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan, March 2020) has identified and analyzed the project target audiences and defined the most appropriate means/tools for reaching the dissemination objectives. This task included also the design and production of all the related dissemination and communication materials, which are presented in the following.

3.1 UNITI-Logos

In cooperation with a graphic designer, a logo was created, which appears in numerous variants on all UNITI products and materials (Figure 1).

Figure 1. UNITI logos

3.2 UNITI- website

The UNITI website (<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net>) is online since January 27 2020 (Figure 2). In addition to basic information such as the project outline, overviews and goals, methodology, composition of the consortium, the website is regularly updated and informs the audience about the progress and the main project results.

Through the website users have access to UNITI's other social media channels on

Instagram (https://www.instagram.com/UNITI_Project/),

Twitter (https://twitter.com/uniti_project),

LinkedIn (<http://www.linkedin.com/in/uniti-project>),

Research Gate (https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Uniti_Project),

Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/unitiproject/>) and

Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/uniti/?page=1&size=20>

[Cordis \(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/848261\)](https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/848261)

The screenshot shows the UNITY website interface. At the top is a blue navigation bar with the UNITY logo and menu items: Home, About UNITY, Research, Public Release, Randomized Clinical Trial, and UNITY BiG Online. Below the navigation bar is a large banner image featuring a group of approximately 30 people standing in front of a building. Each person has a name tag, and the text "UNITY This is us!" is overlaid on the image. Below the banner, there are two main content areas. On the left, a section titled "Unification of Treatments and Interventions for Tinnitus Patients - UNITY" is followed by an article titled "Statistical analysis plan for UNITY-RCT" dated 01 August 2023. On the right, there is a "Social Media" section with icons for Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube, and a "Key Facts" section with a bullet point: "Coordinator: Winfried Schlee, University Clinic Regensburg, AG eHealth".

Figure 2. Screenshot of the UNITY website

3.3 Others

A biannual electronic newsletter kept the consortium up to date on the latest activities and progresses of the project. Videos and interviews produced as part of UNITY are also available to the general public via the TinnitusScience YouTube channel (Figure 3).

Tinnitus Science
@TinnitusScience 731 Abonnenten 105 Videos
What is tinnitus? What do we know about it? >

Abonnieren

ÜBERSICHT VIDEOS LIVE PLAYLISTS KANÄLE KANALINFO

Videos ▶ Alle wiedergeben

Video Title	Duration	Views
#TIWi - Tinnitus Wisdom #10: Summary	2:55	141 Aufrufe - vor 7 Monaten
#TIWi - Tinnitus Wissen #10: Zusammenfassung	3:23	163 Aufrufe - vor 7 Monaten
Merry Christmas to everyone	1:08	185 Aufrufe - vor 7 Monaten
Stochastische Resonanz: Neues Modell zur Erklärung...	20:28	550 Aufrufe - vor 7 Monaten
#TIWi - Tinnitus Wisdom #9: Tinnitus Myths	3:48	165 Aufrufe - vor 7 Monaten
#TIWi - Tinnitus Wissen #9: Tinnitus-Mythen	4:44	143 Aufrufe - vor 7 Monaten

Figure 3. Tinnitus Science (YouTube channel)

4 Communication and Community Building Strategies

4.1 UNITI-TV

1st UNITI online meeting

Figure 4. Invitation to the 1st UNITI online meeting

Due to the drastic changes that took place in all areas of our society around the world with the appearance of the corona virus in March 2020, the UNITI project management also had to rethink its Communication and Community Building Strategies.

While face-to-face consortium meetings were planned for May and September 2020 and January 21 at the kick-off meeting in Athens in January 2020, the Project Management came up with the idea of interim online meetings in order to stay in touch with the UNITI-community and keep them up to date the current status of the UNITI project. The first episode of the UNITI TV series started on May 26, 2020 (Figure 4).

The members of the UNITI consortium and the members of the advisory board received an invitation link with which they could join the GoTo meeting.

The first part of the meeting was always filled with presentations of the work packages and task leaders presenting the progress. Questions could be typed in the FAQ-/Chat and were answered / discussed at the end of the presentations.

For those who were unable to watch a UNITI-TV episode, the episode of about 90 min length was recorded and made available for re-watch in Basecamp.

In total, the UNITI management had invited to 13 UNITI-TV episodes from March 2020 until July 2023.

4.2 RCT working group meetings

Besides the quarterly UNITI-TV episodes the Management established a RCT working group meeting every two weeks, initially via Skype, because of technical reasons later via Zoom. During these meetings, the RCT working group drew up all the documents required to conduct the study and discussed possible risks, especially with regard to the changed conditions caused by the Corona pandemic. Tasks to be completed and decisions made were recorded in a continuous Word document accessible online by all RCT working group members. With the start of the study in April 2021, problems that arose and progress at the study centers with regard to the course of the study were also discussed in these meetings.

4.3 SOPs and RCT-Trainings

For all examinations and/or procedures to be carried out as part of the study SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) were drawn up, and these were also available to the study teams at the centers at any time online via Basecamp. In addition, all study teams were trained by the "speakers" responsible for the respective SOP, if necessary, also in additional individual training. The RCT management team from Regensburg, which took over the overall management of the clinical trial including data quality control, also offered a weekly meeting for each study center to discuss current problematic cases and/or to coordinate the study centers with each other. This offer was used on a weekly basis by the CHA study center from the very beginning of the study, as well as by the KUL at a later point in time. The study centers in Granada and Athens took advantage of the offer at irregular intervals. Beyond these fixed dates, the RCT management team was always available for acute questions and problems.

4.4 Overview Dissemination Results

With regard to dissemination and communication, the most important results during the project period are mentioned here.

4.4.1 Scientific publications

Within the UNITI framework. 43 journal papers were published so far with many more to follow.

Furthermore, nine conference technical papers have been published, amongst others, 1 conference paper has been presented at the 2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA) and 3 conference papers at the 2021 IEEE 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC)..

All published scientific work is available here:

<https://uniti.tinnitusresearch.net/index.php/research/scientific-publications>.

4.4.2 Two internal UNITI “hackathons”

Two UNITI hackathons were organized to build a community of researchers that collaborate together in order to analyze and understand the data from the UNITI project. A large amount of data was collected during the UNITI project, allowing for many data analyses to be conducted. Building such a community of researchers that are already familiar with the data structure, will enable future projects beyond the lifetime of the UNITI project.

3.-5. May 2022
Landshut, Germany
(direct train connection to Munich Airport, 33 min)

Figure 5. Invitation to the first UNITI Hackathon

The first UNITI Hackathon was organized from 3rd to 5th of May 2022 in Landshut, Germany (Figure 5). During this meeting, 5 interdisciplinary teams worked on different data analysis projects (e.g., outcome prediction, subgroup identification).

The second UNITI Hackathon took place from 7th to 9th of February 2023 in Granada, Spain. Here, two groups (data analysis and manuscript writing) worked in parallel to prepare the publication of the UNITI RCT results.

4.4.3 UNITI Meetings

4.4.3.1 Kick-Off Meeting

The Kick-Off Meeting of the UNITI-Project took place from 15-16 January 2020 at the ICCS in Athens. During the kick-off meeting, the individual work packages were presented again and the tasks of those responsible were outlined. A large part of the first few days was taken up by the planning of the clinical study to be carried out. A detailed schedule was drawn up in the large plenary session with the assignment of the tasks to be completed in order to be able to start recruiting patients as soon as possible, but no later than the beginning of 2021. On the second day, the individual working groups came together to develop a joint plan for further action with regard to the tasks to be completed.

4.4.3.2 UNITI-Networking Event – Tinnitus at the Lake

TINNITUS

at the lake

Figure 6: "Tinnitus at the lake" logo.

A first physical meeting of the UNITI consortium after the Corona pandemic took place on 28th and 29th of June 2022 in Herrsching, Germany (called "Tinnitus at the lake") and included discussions and research presentations regarding the UNITI RCT, UNITI datasets/analysis, tinnitus socio-economic study, UNITI DSS (decision support system), genetics, etc (Figure 6).

The final UNITI project meeting will take place from 21st to 23rd of September 2023 in Athens (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Invitation to the final UNITI project meeting

4.4.4 Media Content

Immediately after the EU approved the funding for the UNITI project, a press release with a brief description of the project's objectives was published on the websites of the individual institutions. Moreover some of the local newspapers (Regensburg) reported on the project funding. In January 202 Kick-Off-Meeting the speaker of the external Advisory Board, Prof. Raj Shekhawat posted a Video statement on the UNITI project and ICCS published a Blog Post about the UNITI Kick-Off. In April 2020 the Bayerische Forschungsallianz reported on the project within their regularly Newsletter.

Furthermore UNITI was mentioned in 6 newsletters of the Tinnitus Research Initiative (TRI) and UNITI was featured in the "Tinnitus Forum" magazine (the members' magazine of the German, Swiss and Austrian Tinnitus League and the Hearing Foundation). In parallel, several blog entries were made on the project's website informing about the latest project's activities.

4.4.5 Awards

Miro Schleicher from UNITI team at Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg has received the Marco Ramoni best paper award at the 20th Artificial Intelligence in Medicine (AIME) conference for his paper 'When can I expect the mHealth user to return? Prediction meets time series with gaps' (Miro Schleicher, Rüdiger Pryss, Winfried Schlee and Myra Spiliopoulou).¹

4.4.6 Other than UNITI Meetings and Events

UNITI was presented in several conferences, events and seminars (e.g. Science Night Regensburg 2021 and 2022, 22nd Tinnitussymposium Charité 2021 and 2022, IEE EMBC 2021, 72th National Congress of SEORL-CCC, 2021 ECML PKDD Ghent satellite event, at the Tinnitus at the Lake Meeting 2022 and the TRI2023 Tinnitus Conference in Dublin).

4.4.7 Synergies and Networking

Synergies which had been established with initiatives and projects (e.g. Tinnitus Research Initiative, American Tinnitus Association, Tinnitus UK (former British Tinnitus Association), ESIT project, TIN-ACT project, VITALISE project, ENTICE project) were maintained and further expanded.

In cooperation with the TRI, some UNITI colleagues (Stefan Schoisswohl, Milena Engelke, Susanne Staudinger, Winfried Schlee (UHREG), Ilias Trochidis (VIL)) are now members of the TRI Academy team and are actively involved in the programming of the lecture series as organizers or speakers.

4.4.8 UNITI-BIG

Patients who were unable to take part in the UNITI RCT for a wide variety of reasons (e.g. not meeting the inclusion criteria, long distance to the clinic, recruitment completed) have the opportunity to at least receive the app-based therapy options by participating in the large online study UNITI-BIG. This online study collects longitudinal data on tinnitus symptoms during treatment which may provide important data in the search for an effective treatment of tinnitus.

¹ [https://www.kmd.ovgu.de/News/_Best+paper+award_+at+AIME+2022-p-1538.html#:~:text=Miro%20Schleicher%20has%20received%20the,Winfried%20Schlee%20and%20Myra%20Spiliopoulou\).](https://www.kmd.ovgu.de/News/_Best+paper+award_+at+AIME+2022-p-1538.html#:~:text=Miro%20Schleicher%20has%20received%20the,Winfried%20Schlee%20and%20Myra%20Spiliopoulou).)

Overview Dissemination, Communication and Community Building

	Level of reach			Target group				
	Internal	external EU level	External global	researchers	clinicians	patients	industry	Policy makers
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletter	✓	✓		✓	✓			
youTube	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UNITI-TV	✓			✓	✓			
RCT WG*	✓			✓	✓			
SOP/RCT Trainings	✓			✓	✓			
Hackathon1	✓	✓		✓	✓			
Hackathon2	✓	✓		✓	✓			
Tinnitus at the Lake Event	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
TRI congress Dublin and others	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Synergies and Networking	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Media Content	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
BIG Online	✓	✓	✓			✓		

5 Conclusion

The corona pandemic has brought major restrictions on public life. Curfews, bans on contact, the maintenance of safety distances and strict hygiene regulations posed particular challenges for the UNITI Consortium.

In summary, the UNITI Consortium can proudly look back on a successful project duration despite the difficult conditions caused by the Corona Pandemic. The fact that the study on the scale of the UNITI RCT was able to be brought to a successful conclusion under the most massive restrictions, such as bans on contact and experiments, strict hygiene regulations in clinics, compulsory tests for staff and study participants, to name just a few, is just a fact owing to the highly motivated and disciplined consortium members as well as the prudent and forward-looking organization of the project management. According to the circumstances, online meetings were held regularly, while in-person meetings were organised whenever possible. During the project period, it was possible to further expand the network that existed from previous projects and to use it for synergy effects, for example with regard to patient care beyond the UNITI RCT.